

An aerial view: a top down approach to digitisation using whole drawing imaging

Miss Elizabeth Devenish¹, Ms Robyn Crowther¹

¹*The Natural History Museum, London, United Kingdom*

Unlocking specimen data through digitisation is the goal of many natural history museums, but often this mammoth task is limited by available resources. Alternatively, capturing data for a group of specimens may be a more cost and time efficient process, providing a basis for future digitisation of individual objects.

The Natural History Museum, London (NHM) is currently preparing for the largest collections move in its history. This will require capturing data to track specimens moving between locations, and documenting conservation status. Where possible, this will be completed for individual specimens, however certain collections are of such high-volume that it will be impossible to complete this in time and within budget. One such collection is the Museum's nine million specimens of pinned Coleoptera, which will instead require data capture at a broader level.

By imaging individual drawers, this level of data can be documented quickly, capturing an overall specimen count, label data, presence of type material, and a basic conservation condition assessment. Drawers of pinned entomological specimens particularly lend themselves to this imaging approach. A photographic reference of a collection also has the advantage of allowing a user to examine the contents of each drawer remotely, likely to be particularly valuable in light of the COVID-19 pandemic and resulting lockdowns.

Using a portion of the NHM's 28,000 drawers of pinned Coleoptera specimens, we completed a project comparing two contemporary imaging setups: a high-cost scanner and comparatively low cost camera and light box. In this presentation, we will evaluate the differences in image quality, capture rates and overall costs of each method, whilst addressing limitations in historical drawer scanning projects. We will also discuss the potential replicability and utility in other collection types and museums, as well as the use of images both by curators and external users via the NHM's open-access data portal.

